

ON THE OPTIMIZATION STUDIES OF FORGING OF 359/SiC/20p

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ABSTRACT

The hot formability of 359/SiC/20p was studied at temperatures ranging from 375 to 500°C, and strain rates from 0.003 to 10 s⁻¹. The optimum plastic flow condition is obtained at 500°C and 0.003 s⁻¹. A constitutive equation, giving the relationship between flow stress and working parameters, was successfully obtained. Closed-die forging trials on H-section components were carried out with a workpiece temperature of 420°C, upper and lower die temperatures of 310 and 250°C, respectively, and die speed of about 10 mm/s. The forgings show the presence in the flash and in the internal corner regions of high volume fractions of voids at the matrix-particulate interfaces due to the high strain rates that reduce the strain to failure of the MMC. The forging conditions can be improved mainly by decreasing the die speed of the process.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand in the car industry for low weight and high performance materials makes metal matrix composites (MMCs), based on aluminium alloys reinforced with particles of ceramic materials such as SiC and Al₂O₃, very attractive for such applications. MMCs are candidates to replace steels in components such as connecting rods and suspension arms; however, the high ductility and fracture toughness values required to satisfy car safety rules are very difficult to achieve in MMC components and widely reduce the field of application of MMCs in the automotive industry. Therefore, the study of the optimum manufacturing conditions permitting the satisfaction of the heavy requirements of car industry is very important in order to exploit the full potential of MMCs in reducing weight in such applications.

Particulate-reinforced aluminium matrix composites can be hot forged, like aluminium alloys, by conventional forging processes [1]. However, MMCs are more sensitive to temperature and strain rate conditions than the unreinforced matrices mainly due to the debonding at the particle-matrix interface occurring when the shear stress that develops at the interface exceeds the strength of the interface [1-7]; such phenomenon leads to mechanical properties lower than the expected ones. Therefore, obtaining and maintaining suitable temperature and strain rate of the workpiece during forging operations of MMCs is very critical to the success of the process. For given deforming material and component shape, this can be obtained only by a proper definition of workpiece and die temperatures, die speed, lubrication, and design.

In the present paper, the hot formability of a MMC was investigated in extended ranges of temperature and strain rate. The results of such studies were used to evaluate the optimum

working conditions; furthermore, the constitutive equation, giving the correlation among flow stress, strain, strain rate, and temperature, was calculated for its implementation into numerical codes based on the finite element method (FEM). Finally, a microstructural damage analysis of the forged components was carried out in order to correlate the void formation in the MMC under investigation to the working conditions of the forging trials.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material used, 359/SiC/20p, was produced by Duralcan, USA, by mixing SiC powders, with an average size of 12.8 μm , into molten A 359 aluminium alloy; after casting, foundry ingots were extruded, with an extrusion ratio of 13, into 80 mm diameter rods. The billets were then thermal treated at 540°C for 4 h and air cooled. The nominal chemical composition of the A 359 alloy is the following: 8.5-9.5 Si, 0.2 Fe, 0.2 Cu, 0.50-0.70 Mg, 0.10 Zn, 0.20 Ti, Al balance.

The hot formability studies were performed by means of torsion tests that permit large strains without the limitation imposed by necking in tension tests or by barreling in compression tests [8]. The tests were carried out, until rupture of the samples, on a servo-controlled hydraulic torsion machine, at temperatures varying from 375 to 500°C, and equivalent strain rates ($\dot{\epsilon}$) at the specimen surface from 0.003 to 10 s^{-1} . The samples were quickly heated by high frequency induction coil (3°C/s); a thermocouple was inserted down the axis in a shoulder near the gauge section of the specimen to control the temperature throughout the test. The specimens were machined from the rods with the axis parallel to the extrusion direction. The gauge section of the samples was a solid cylinder with a length of 7 mm, and a radius of 4 mm; the fillet radius between the gauge section and the shoulders was 0.5 mm. Equivalent stresses (σ) and strains (ϵ) were derived from surface shear stresses and strains by means of the von Mises criterion [8]. The flow curves for $\dot{\epsilon} \geq 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ do not correspond to isothermal conditions due to the temperature increase produced by deformation heating; therefore, temperature correction was applied to the σ - ϵ data in such conditions according to [9].

Forging trials were performed at Stampal SpA, Italy, by means of a hydraulic press with a maximum capacity of 5000 tons at 300 bars. The initial billets, with a diameter of 80 mm, 250 mm length; were heated at the temperature of 420°C for 1.5 h in a resistance furnace with forced ventilation; the dies were preheated in a furnace at 500°C and, after die set up, held by gas burners at the temperature of about 310°C for the upper die and 250°C for the lower die, measured by means of two thermocouples inserted into the dies. The speed of the mobile die was pressure dependent. Video records, performed during several forging trials, have shown a velocity variation throughout the process; however, a constant die speed of 10 mm/s was assumed [10-11]. The lubricant used in the forging trials was a water-graphite solution (10:1 ratio) sprayed on a layer of animal fat with lead oxide. The H-section selected for the closed-die forging trials was the result of the widespread use of this section in automotive components such as connecting rods and suspension link arms.

RESULTS

FORMABILITY RESULTS

The flow curves of 359/SiC/20p are characterized by an increase of σ with strain up to a maximum value that is followed by a stationary state or by a very limited flow softening until fracture (Fig. 1). The flow stress versus temperature curves, at different strain rates, with constant

strain, are shown in Fig. 2; flow stress decreases with increasing temperature and decreasing strain rate following the typical behaviour of metals deformed in hot working conditions [1-8, 12-13]. The ductility, measured as equivalent strain to failure (ϵ_f), versus temperature, at constant strain rates, is shown in Fig. 3; it increases with decreasing strain rate. Furthermore, ϵ_f increases with temperature up to a maximum value that usually appears at temperatures ranging from 450 to 475°C; at lower strain rates, ϵ_f monotonically increases with temperature. The hot formability studies show that the most favourable working condition to forge 359/SiC/20p is characterized by the highest temperature (500°C) and the lowest strain rate (0.003 s⁻¹) since it offers the best combination between flow stress and ductility. However, it is the worst working condition from an economical point of view mainly due to the low production rate.

Fig. 1 Flow curves of 359/SiC/20p.

Fig. 2 Flow stress vs. temperature plots at different strain rates.

Fig. 3 Ductility vs. temperature curves at different strain rates.

Fig. 4 Strain rate vs. $\sinh(\alpha\sigma)$ plots at all the temperatures investigated.

CONSTITUTIVE EQUATION

The flow stress data for the 359/SiC/20p was obtained by using a phenomenological approach consisting of the determination of the equation given by Sellars and Tegart [13] as a function of strain. The flow stress versus strain, strain rate and temperature is obtained by the equation:

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \sinh^{-1} \left[\frac{\dot{\epsilon} \exp \frac{Q(\epsilon)}{RT}}{A(\epsilon)} \right]^{\frac{1}{n(\epsilon)}} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \sinh^{-1} \left[\frac{Z(\epsilon)}{A(\epsilon)} \right]^{\frac{1}{n(\epsilon)}} \quad (1)$$

where Q is the activation energy of the deformation process, Z is the Zener-Hollomon parameter, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, and α , A, and n are material parameters. The activation energy was calculated by the relationship:

$$Q = -R \left. \frac{\partial \ln \dot{\epsilon}}{\partial (1/T)} \right|_{\sigma} = 2.3 R \left. \frac{\partial \log \dot{\epsilon}}{\partial \log [\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]} \right|_{\epsilon, T} \left. \frac{\partial \log [\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]}{\partial (1000/T)} \right|_{\epsilon, \dot{\epsilon}} \quad (2)$$

No significant influence of strain on Q was observed; therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the activation energy is independent of strain [8,13]. The plots used to calculate Q are shown in Figs. 4 and 5; it can be seen that in general the slope of the $\log(\dot{\epsilon})-\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]$ and $\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]-1000/T$ plots, at different temperatures and strain rates, respectively, are similar so that the temperature and strain rate effects on Q can be neglected. Therefore, the mean values of the slopes of $\log(\dot{\epsilon})-\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]$ and $\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]-1000/T$ curves equal to 4.60 and 1.91, respectively, lead to an activation energy value of 168 kJ/mol. The stress multiplier α was calculated by means of an optimization procedure: the α value of 0.022 gave the best correlation coefficient for the linear relationships $\log(\dot{\epsilon})-\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]$ and $\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]-1000/T$. Also the material parameter n, the slope of the $\log(Z)-\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]$ plot at constant strain (Fig. 6), is not significantly influenced by ϵ ; therefore, a mean value of n equal to 4.51 was assumed. Contrarily to the behaviour of n and Q, the material parameter A of Eqn (1), representing the intercept of $\log(Z)-\log[\sinh(\alpha\sigma)]$ plot, has shown a dependence on strain (Fig. 7); in particular, in the strain range from 0.3 to 1.3, A increases with ϵ . The values of n and A for $\epsilon < 0.3$ were not considered due to the anomalous low strain behaviour, still to be investigated, of the flow

Fig. 5 Log $\sinh(\alpha\sigma)$ vs. $1000/T$ plots at all the strain rates investigated.

Fig. 6 Temperature compensated strain rate vs. $\sinh(\alpha\sigma)$ plot.

Fig. 7 A parameter vs. strain plot.

Fig. 8 Comparison between predicted (symbols) and experimental (lines) flow curves.

curves obtained at higher strain rates (Fig. 1). For $\epsilon > 1.3$, the limited number of experimental data due to the failure of the samples tested at higher strain rates does not permit a reliable computation of n and A . The A versus ϵ curve can be described by a linear equation with the material constants obtained by the least square fitting. The resulting relationship is:

$$A = 2.10 \times 10^{11} + 4.54 \times 10^{10} \epsilon \quad (3)$$

The predicted flow curves at 425°C, for all the strain rates investigated, obtained by means of Eqn (1), with $\alpha=0.022$, $n = 4.51$, $Q=168$ kJ/mol, and the value of A given by Eqn (3), are shown in Fig. 8 where they are compared to the experimental ones. The flow curves were obtained for ϵ varying from 0.1 to the strain to failure. In the strain range from 0.3 to ϵ_f , the predicted flow stress is in excellent agreement with the measured one. For $\epsilon < 0.3$, at higher strain rates, the predicted flow stress is generally higher than the experimental one.

FORGING RESULTS

Closed-die forging trials were performed in temperature and strain rate conditions which differ from the optimum ones evaluated by the hot formability studies on 359\SiC\20p; in particular, the workpiece temperature (420°C) is lower and the die speed (about 10 mm/s) is higher than the ones where the maximum formability was achieved. Such experiments were carried out at the same workpiece temperature of most unreinforced aluminium alloys but with a higher die temperature and a lower die speed [9] in order to find an acceptable combination between the need to minimize component cost and the requirement of high strength component.

The H-section components obtained with a single step forging operation show no macroscale defects; the die cavity is filled with dimensional and geometrical features of the forgings consistent with the design ones. The microstructural observations by means of optical microscopy in the transversal section of the forged components (Fig. 9) show that the volume fraction of voids at the matrix-particulate interfaces in the internal corner zone nearest the external border (region A), and in the flash zone (region B), is higher than the one in the other zones of the workpiece (i.e., region C).

Fig. 9 Optical micrographs showing the structure in different zones of the H-section forging.

DISCUSSION

The analysis of the flow curves of 359/SiC/20p has shown that the flow stress and ductility are strongly dependent on the working conditions. It is well known that the plastic flow behaviour of MMCs is more influenced by working conditions than unreinforced aluminium alloys [1-8, 12-13]. At lower temperatures and higher strain rates, the flow behaviour of MMCs is controlled by the reinforcing phase which is responsible for the higher flow stress and lower ductility than the matrix [14]. At higher temperatures and lower strain rates, the increased effectiveness of diffusional processes prevents an excessive increase in stress concentration at the matrix-particulate interfaces and leads to a structure which is similar to the unreinforced one [14]. In the present investigation, reliable experimental data on A 359 aluminium alloy are not yet available; however, the value of the activation energy of 359/SiC/20p (168 kJ/mol), similar to the one of several aluminium alloys [5,8,12], should be attributed to the microstructural features of the matrix that control the hot deformation behaviour of the MMC.

The full potential of the metal-forming modelling techniques based on FEM analysis can be exploited through the precise characterization of the MMC flow behaviour; in particular, there is a demand for information on the strain dependence of stress at each temperature and strain rate. The Eqn (1) accounts for strain rate and temperature sensitivity by means of the Zener-Hollomon parameter. Furthermore, the sensitivity of A , Q , and n to the various restoration mechanisms taking place during the deformation process, offers the advantage of the development of a more general procedure for calculating flow stress data without choosing a priori which restoration mechanisms may be operating during deformation.

In metal-forming, defect-free items can be obtained only avoiding that damage mechanisms take place during the deformation. Such a condition is very difficult to achieve when high strength and low ductility materials such as MMCs are forged, mainly due to the high strain rates arising in some zones of the workpiece. The high volume fraction of voids in the internal corner and

flash regions of the 359/SiC/20p forgings (Fig. 9) is in excellent agreement with the results obtained by Roberts et al. [10-11] with the same working conditions and H-section component of the present investigation but using AA 2618/Al₂O₃/20p. They predicted, by means of a FEM analysis of the forging operation, a maximum $\dot{\epsilon}$ of 5.6 s⁻¹, with a corresponding strain of 2, in the flash region, and a maximum $\dot{\epsilon}$ of 0.8, with a corresponding strain of 1.3, in the internal corner zone. The high volume fraction of voids in such regions is consistent with the theory proposed by Humphreys and Kalu [15]. According to this theory, below a critical strain rate, which increases with temperature, there will be no build up of stress at the matrix-reinforcement interfaces: no fracture induced by the high local stresses is expected. When the strain rate exceeds the critical value, stress concentration at the particles during deformation will produce the debonding of the particulate-matrix interfaces. By using the FEM simulations of Roberts et al. [10-11] in the present investigation, it can be observed that the predicted strains in the flash region are higher than the values of ductility derived from the hot formability studies on 359/SiC/20p at similar strain rates, irrespective of workpiece temperature (Fig. 3). Such behaviour also appears, with less evidence, in the internal corner zone. In the other zones of the workpiece, the lower strain rate results in more favourable plastic flow conditions; actually, in such regions the ductility is higher than the predicted strain. Furthermore, the void closure occurring in such zones during forging owing to the hydrostatic component of the stress state increases the strain that can be applied without failure. On the contrary, the flash area is not subjected to the hydrostatic constraints that are present in the other zones of the forging. Such effects cannot be predicted through the ductility measured by the torsion tests.

The microstructural damage in the flash and internal corner regions can be reduced by decreasing the die speed and increasing the workpiece temperature. However, by considering the $\dot{\epsilon}$ values predicted in such zones and the workpiece temperature, the ductility versus temperature curves (Fig. 3) suggest that the decrease in strain rate is more effective than the increase in temperature in reducing the occurrence of the damage mechanisms at the matrix-particulate interfaces. An optimization procedure can be used to calculate the lowest die speed and the highest workpiece temperature. However, for slower forging operations, die temperature usually controls the actual workpiece temperature during deformation and becomes a critical parameter in the process optimization. In the present case, the dies should be heated at higher temperatures than the ones for the faster forging operation since lower strain rates lead to a large workpiece cooling. Such a decrease in temperature reduces the ductility and acts in an opposite way to the decrease of strain rate.

CONCLUSIONS

The hot formability studies on 359/SiC/20p have established that a temperature of 500°C and a strain rate of 0.003 s⁻¹ represent the optimum working conditions since they offer the best combination between flow stress and ductility. The plastic flow behaviour is well described by a constitutive equation giving the hyperbolic sine of stress versus temperature modified strain rate and strain. Closed-die forging trials, performed with a workpiece temperature of 420°C, upper and lower die temperatures of 310 and 250°C, respectively, and die speed of about 10 mm/s, have shown that the H-shape of the dies is filled without the appearance of surface macrocracks. The microstructural damage analysis on a transversal section of the forgings has shown the void formation at the matrix-particulate interfaces in the flash and internal corner regions. In such zones, the temperature and strain rate conditions experienced lead to ductility values that are lower than accumulated plastic strains; therefore, the ductility can be effectively used, in conjunction with the FEM analysis of the forging, for the prediction of the void formation in the workpiece even if void closure due to hydrostatic constraints cannot be predicted. The forging conditions can be improved mainly by reducing the die speed.

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